

MODERN METHODS FOR DETERMINING THE CAUSES AND CONDITIONS OF ORGANIZED CRIME

Mukhammadkhanov Sherzod Yashinovich

IV 3rd year cadet of the Academy, safdor

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Annotation: Through this article, you can learn about the causes of the commission of organized crime and the types of organized crime, the risks posed by organized crime in society, the cause and condition of the commission criminologically, and the prospects for the application of national and foreign experience of the fight against crime in practice.

Keywords: *organized crime, cause, conditions of condition, Russian experience, methods.*

Introduction

Committing a crime by a group of persons previously conspired is not news to law enforcement agencies. It is not necessary to repeat that these crimes are socially dangerous and, as a rule, cause more harm to social relations protected by criminal law.

According to criminal statistics, in subsequent years there is a sharp increase in the number of crimes

grouped, organized and increased social danger.

The need to develop appropriate forensic recommendations for the prevention, disclosure and investigation of crimes committed by organized criminal groups to make them more effective, to organize their investigation was ensured. This determines the relevance of the chosen topic .

In criminal law, there is no concept of organized criminal activity. The definition of "organized crime" was given in 1975 in the United States by the Ministry of Justice and the FBI for use in special programs to combat this phenomenon. According to this definition, organized crime is the ability of the main activity of any group of persons to violate criminal laws in order to obtain illegal income, as well as to engage in racketeering and, if necessary, complex financial manipulations.

It should be noted that at present there are other definitions of organized crime, but the essence lies in one thing - the organization (Group), the presence of the culture formed in it and the practice of criminal entrepreneurship. At the same time, definitions often contain not elements that characterize organized crime as a social phenomenon, but criminal and legal signs that define the concept of organized crime.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Organized crime - this is a relatively mass activity of stable managed communities, which, as a type of entrepreneurship, are engaged in criminal activity and create a system of protection against corruption, as well as social and legal control of the state by other means. Organized crime itself is

a social phenomenon, but it is impossible to criminalize a social phenomenon – only certain types of activity are subject to criminal liability.

Analysis of the current criminal law, literary sources and the practice of solving crimes committed by participants in organized criminal structures is the only one in accordance with certain rules of organized criminal activity has leadership allows you to identify actions aimed at committing a crime by a combined group of people who have been involved in a crime. plan. In turn, in the sense of the current criminal law in an organized criminal structure, a partnership such as committing a crime by an organized group or criminal community should be understood by a group of individuals in advance .

In the last decades of the 20th century, there has been a rapid increase in organized crime in the world. This threatening trend is associated with significant advances in technology and communication and an unprecedented expansion of international commercial and economic activity. Transnational criminal organizations make good use of the current international situation. As a result, crime not only expands, but also brings income. Organized crime is becoming international. The markets for the sale

of weapons, drugs, stolen goods and other illegal goods and services are expanding. The total volume of these operations is hundreds of billions of dollars. This situation forced the international community to unite their efforts in the fight against Transnational Organized Crime and proceed to the development of a conceptual apparatus of organized criminal activity.

A generalized description of organized crime is given in the report of the UN secretary general on April 13-23 "the impact of organized crime on society as a whole" at the second session of the UN Economic and Social Council Commission on crime prevention and criminal justice. , 1993. To some extent, it provides a list of signs that will help explain the essence of this phenomenon:

a) organized crime is the activity of criminal associations or groups united on an economic basis. These groups are reminiscent of the feudal era gangs that existed in Europe in the Middle Ages. Economic interests are obtained by them through the provision of illegal services and goods or the provision of legal services and goods in violation of the law;

b) organized crime, implies a conspiratorial criminal activity in which, with the help of hierarchically structured structures, the planning

and implementation of illegal actions or the achievement of legal goals with the help of illegal means are coordinated;

c) organized criminal groups tend to impose a partial or complete monopoly on the provision of illegal goods and services to consumers, since a high income is guaranteed through it;

d) organized crime is not limited to knowingly carrying out illegal activities or providing illegal services. It also includes complex activities such as legal economic structures and money laundering through electronic manipulation. Illegal criminal groups penetrate many useful legal activities;

e) criminals, divided into groups, use in their "work" various measures that can be complex and delicate, or, conversely, rude, direct and open. They are used to establish a monopoly on the provision of illegal goods and services, to penetrate into the legal activities of corrupt officials. Thus, when individuals involved in organized crime engage in legal entrepreneurial activity, they introduce methods of violence and intimidation, which are usually used in illegal activities .

As a continuation of these cases, at the 53rd Session of the UN General Assembly (December 9, 1998), it was decided to prepare the UN Convention Against

Transnational Organized Crime, including provisions on the organization of criminal activities and the introduction of criminal liability for participation in it. teams, money laundering, corruption and justice resistance. At the same time, it was decided to develop three protocols that complement the Convention: on the prevention, putting an end to it and punishing trafficking in human beings, especially women and children; smuggling migrants by land, sea and air; preparation and circulation of firearms, their components, components and ammunition in violation of the law.

Bykov V.M. we agree that the organized criminal group is characterized by the following signs: stability of the group's personal composition; the purpose of grouping is to constantly commit crimes; the presence of a psychological structure formed in the group, as a result of which the leader comes to the fore in the group; distribution of roles in the preparation, Commission and concealment of crimes; planning and division into a group according to the place held by each member in the composition; creation of a special monetary factor in the group.

There are also organized criminal groups divided into ethnic,

cultural and historical ties. Such contacts connect them with the countries of origin and thus create a large criminal network that exceeds national borders. Using common origin, language, traditions, they are able to protect themselves from the actions of law enforcement agencies. Many organized criminal groups are known by their ethnic or national names. Due to their prevalence and lack of alternatives, these names are used in science and practice, although such terms are characterized by being overly simplified .

Penetrating into the field of Economics and management, organized crime is also assessed differently by law enforcement and legislative bodies of the state. In recent years, there has been a tendency for smaller but more resilient mobile groups of criminals to proliferate, which undoubtedly gives them greater security. It has eight main features:

1) to form a group with the aim of dealing with crimes as a profession for more or less time;

2) centralization of power in the hands of one or more members of the group;

3) creation of funds for the needs of the organization;

4) specialization of the holistic group in certain crimes and the

distribution of functions within the group;

5) monopolistic trends;

6) corruption, expressed in the creation of a system of relations with judges, police officers, doctors, politicians, the administration;

7) establishment of strict discipline, strict adherence to established rules of conduct;

8) careful planning with minimal risk.

Organized crime is characterized by the following systematized elements: racketeering, prostitution, drug smuggling, organization of criminal entrepreneurship in the form of gambling; groups committing crimes that serve as a source of livelihood; improvement of criminal activity and isolation from society; presence of economically based risk; concealing criminal activity; support for organized crime by politicians and police. A similar crime is observed in Italy and Japan, at the same time, German experts emphasize the danger of organized crime, understand it and characterize stable groups involved in various types of selfish and violent crimes.

The Russian criminal world entered the 19th century as a fortified, holistic, holistic world, which had the power to oppose public order and law. Its traditions, customs,

"laws" are in the minds of entire generations of offenders

However, the emergence of the "Russian mafia" was hampered by the lack of market and strong military-political state power in the Russian Empire, which "broke the waist" of potential competitors.

In the pre-revolutionary period (1917), in the context of the economic and political crisis, trade, financial, industrial and bureaucratic organized crime arose in the country. The black market has blocked the ordinary market many times. Corruption covered the apparatus associated with financial and commodity flows.

The revolution of 1917 and subsequent events radically changed the situation in the Russian criminal world. In the first years after the revolution, many professional criminals were released, part of which even came to serve in the Cheka and the police. Thus, the age-old laws of thieves were violated. At the same time, former members of the gendarmerie, defeated White Army officers, United into organized gangs.

By the end of the 1920s, a certain crisis had arisen in the distribution of spheres of influence in the criminal world. Constant clashes between different groups necessitated the need to improve the "laws" of Thieves. As a result, on

the basis of past traditions and Customs, a single "law" of Thieves arose, according to which the most respected criminals were called "thieves in law". It is to this period that some principles of the activities of "Thieves in law" belong, which still retain their significance to this day:

Collective solution of complex issues both in places of imprisonment and in "outside" meetings;

The restoration of the Common Fund as a material base of criminals, the formation of their bases, communities, "raspberries" in each settlement by thieves in law;

To comply with the "law" of revenge to abandon the observance of the traditions and customs of Thieves.

Conclusion

From the mid-1930s, along with political terror, repressive measures were intensified against professional criminals. The criminal world was again pushed underground and forced to fight for survival in prisons. "During Stalin's time and in the pre-war years, professional crime was dealt a serious blow.

Khrushchev's "melting", liberalization of criminal punishment, attempts at the first economic reforms prompted the criminal world to change its course. Professional crime, consisting of gangs of criminals, acquired a completely different qualitative state, very similar

to such a phenomenon in bourgeois countries that developed in a new social context. "First, a network structure of the organization appeared, according to which it became possible and even inevitable to divide spheres and territories between groups. Secondly, ordinary criminals also united with thieves representatives of the state apparatus. Groups of criminals have entered the economy and society, even politics. The latter is typical of organized crime".

During this period, a secret economy begins to take shape. Underground dealers increased criminal revenues. At first, acting secretly and carefully, they correctly emphasized E.G. Andryushchenko went out with arrogance and arrogance.

By the mid-1980s, a highly organized anti-social forces had emerged in society: the party-state bureaucracy and the corrupt part of mafia structures. It was they who poured into the space formed during the disintegration of administrative structures, actively demolished these structures and enriched themselves in conditions of chaos. As a result of the campaign against alcohol, large initial capital fell into the hands of criminals, which not only caused a deficit in the state budget, but also contributed to the emergence of

new stable mafia structures and the rapid growth of shadow. capital.

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